

| The European Synchrotron

Presenter: Philipp BRUMUND

Remote Points

- A** Bottom
- B** Top
- C** Piezo Force Stack- End
- D** Piezo Stack- Mid
- E** Piezo Sensor Stack- End

Multibody Simulations with Reduced Order Flexible Bodies Obtained by FEA

Brumund, Philipp
Dehaeze, Thomas

Flexible Bodies in Simscape

- **Multibody simulation:** applied for development of new nano-endstation

- Hexapod

- *MATLAB Simscape* for control design

- Possibility to use reduced order flexible bodies

- Consideration of bodies elastic and inertial properties in simulations (of arbitrary shape)

E: Modal Only Plateau
Mode Twist: 425 Hz
Type: Total Deformation
Frequency: 425.3 Hz
Unit: mm
12/07/2021 10:56

8.9736 Max
8.3257
7.6778
7.0299
6.3821
5.7342
5.0863
4.4394
3.7906
3.1427 Min

•Reduced order models obtained via FEA

•Procedure developed for *modal* reduction with ANSYS (FEA)

- **Effective Reduction** of FEA degrees of freedom (>100k) to small number of “retained” ones

Detailed explanations:

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5092055>

FEA reduced order model

+ *Simscape*

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Testbench

Comparison:

Testbench / *Simscape*
+ red. order model

➤ Confirms method

- **Additional info on procedure in**

- Paper

- Appendices with detailed explanations and helpful ANSYS APDL code snippets

- <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5092055>

- **If more info wanted: write us! 😊**